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O'ZBEKISTONDAGI NODAVLAT OLIY TA'LIM TASHKILOTLARIDA MOLIYAVIY REJALASHTIRISH METODOLOGIYASI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu ilmiy tadqiqotda O'zbekistondagi nodavlat oliy ta'lim tashkilotlari (NOTT) uchun moliyaviy rejalashtirish va moliyalashtirish mexanizmlari tahlil qilingan. NOTT moliyaviy barqarorligini ta'minlashda asosiy daromad manbalari – kontrakt to'lovlari, grantlar, ta'sischi mablag'lari va hamkorlik loyihalarining roli batafsil yoritilgan. Shuningdek, strategik rejalashtirish, byudjetni samarali boshqarish, xarajatlarni optimallashtirish va diversifikatsiyalangan moliyalashtirish modellaridan foydalanish bo'yicha amaliy tavsiyalar berilgan. Tadqiqot natijalari NOTT moliyaviy mustaqilligini oshirish hamda ularning uzoq muddatli barqaror rivojlanishini ta'minlashga xizmat qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: nodavlat oliy ta'lim tashkilotlari, moliyaviy rejalashtirish, byudjet boshqaruvi, diversifikatsiyalangan moliyalashtirish, daromad manbalari, moliyaviy mustaqillik, strategik rejalashtirish, qabul tendensiyalari.

Abstract: This scientific study analyzes financial planning and funding mechanisms for non-state higher education institutions (NSHEIs) in Uzbekistan. The role of key revenue sources tuition fees, grants, founder investments, and partnership projects in ensuring NSHEIs' financial sustainability is examined in detail. Additionally, practical recommendations are provided on strategic planning, efficient budget management, cost optimization, and the use of diversified funding models. The research findings contribute to enhancing the financial independence of NSHEIs and ensuring their long-term sustainable development.

Key words: non-state higher education institutions, financial planning, budget management, diversified funding, revenue sources, financial independence, strategic planning, enrollment trends.

Аннотация: В данном научном исследовании анализируются механизмы финансового планирования и финансирования негосударственных высших учебных заведений (НВУЗ) в Узбекистане. Детально рассмотрена роль ключевых источников доходов – контрактных платежей, грантов, инвестиций учредителей и партнерских проектов – в обеспечении финансовой устойчивости НВУЗ. Кроме того, представлены практические рекомендации по стратегическому планированию, эффективному управлению бюджетом, оптимизации затрат и использованию диверсифицированных моделей финансирования. Результаты исследования способствуют повышению финансовой независимости НВУЗ и обеспечению их долгосрочного устойчивого развития.

Ключевые слова: негосударственные высшие учебные заведения, финансовое планирование, управление бюджетом, диверсифицированное финансирование, источники доходов, финансовая независимость, стратегическое планирование, тенденции набора студентов.

INTRODUCTION

The financial sustainability and development of higher education institutions are directly linked to effective financial planning and management. In particular, for non-state higher education institutions (NSHEIs), diversified funding sources, financial strategies, and planning methods play a crucial role. This study analyzes the financial planning methodology of NSHEIs, examining funding sources, planning principles, and key components of budget management.

Based on global practices, the funding system of NSHEIs is formed through various sources, including government subsidies, private sector investments, international grants, and student tuition fees. In the case of Uzbekistan, there is a growing trend toward enhancing the financial independence of non-state higher education institutions. Therefore, this study aims to explore the key aspects of effective financial planning for NSHEIs and proposes scientifically grounded approaches to ensuring financial sustainability.

LITERATURE REVIEW IF THE TOPIC

The financial planning methodology in non-state higher education institutions (NSHEIs) in Uzbekistan has become a critical area of research, especially in the context of ongoing higher education reforms. Studies by Valiev and Khurramov (2022) and Meliksetyan (2016) highlight the need for improved financial planning mechanisms, aligning with state policies to enhance efficiency and sustainability. The “Concept for the Development of the Higher Education System until 2030” (Mirkasimov, n.d.; Rasulov, 2024) emphasizes financial diversification and budget optimization to strengthen NSHEIs. Further research by Karlibaeva Gulshat (2023) and Kuvandikov Farrukh (2024) explores best practices in financial resource formation and optimization, emphasizing sustainable funding approaches and risk management strategies in NSHEIs. To ensure long-term stability and competitiveness, NSHEIs must adopt structured financial planning, diversified funding sources, and efficient budget management strategies (Ministry of Higher Education, Science, and Innovation, 2023).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research for this article adopted a mixed-methods approach, combining both qualitative and quantitative research methods to provide a comprehensive analysis of financial planning methodology in NSHEIs. This approach ensures a holistic understanding of the financial mechanisms, challenges, and opportunities in the sector.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Financial planning in non-state higher education institutions (NSHEIs) is the process of forecasting, budgeting, and controlling the institution’s financial resources. Unlike state-funded higher education institutions, which receive financial support from the government, non-state higher education institutions primarily rely on student tuition fees, contributions from institutional founders, grants, and other private sector sources. Therefore, a clear and effective financial plan is essential to ensure the institution’s long-term sustainability and financial stability. The financing of NSHEIs involves several key stages, including identifying funding sources, developing a financial plan, implementing it, and conducting monitoring and reporting. These stages are fundamental components of financial management, ensuring the effective operation and sustainable development of institutions.

Financial Planning for Non-state Organizations

In the financial planning process for non-state organizations, several key factors must be considered, including the objectives and tasks of the business plan, the institution’s marketing strategy, and current market conditions. Additionally, a comprehensive financial plan should include several essential components, such as:

- Revenue and expenditure planning
- Cash flow projections
- Capital expenditure planning

These elements are interrelated and form the foundation of the overall financial plan, which, in turn, is an integral part of the organization’s business strategy. Effective financial planning and management in non-state higher education institutions (NSHEIs) play a crucial role in ensuring their long-term financial stability, competitiveness, and ability to meet student and market demands.

Global Trends in Higher Education Funding

Our research findings indicate that a significant portion of higher education institutions worldwide is funded through public finances. Examples of this include government subsidies, incentives, grants, social support programs, and various forms of targeted funding. However, in recent years, we have observed a shift in the financial burden of higher education funding from the state towards students, their families, and employers.

Moreover, in addition to government funding, universities are increasingly generating their own revenues and securing additional financial resources through private sector contributions and international partnerships. This trend enhances the self-financing capacity of higher education institutions, fostering their sustainable development.

Financial planning in non-state higher education institutions is divided into several key elements as follows:

Budgeting

Budgeting in non-governmental higher education institutions typically includes both operational and capital expenditures. The main areas of expenditure include:

- Salaries and benefits for faculty members;
- Infrastructure development and maintenance;

- Development of research and academic programs;
- Student services.

During the budgeting process, two main approaches are applied: *top-down* and *bottom-up*. These approaches ensure different levels of financial planning and management (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Two Main Approaches to the Budgeting Process.

Top-Down Approach

In this approach, financial planning and key budget indicators are determined by the top management. Decisions are made based on the strategic goals set by the top management. Resources are allocated to lower-level departments with expected outcomes defined.

Advantages:

- ✓ Faster planning process.
- × Strong alignment with strategic objectives.

Disadvantages:

- × The opinions of lower-level departments may not be adequately considered.

Bottom-Up Approach

In this approach, departments or teams assess their needs and capabilities and develop their own budgets. Each department proposes its own expenses and financial plans. These proposals are later consolidated into the overall budget by the management.

Advantages:

- ✓ Encourages employee participation.
- ✓ Improves communication and initiative.

Disadvantages:

- × The process can be time-consuming.
- × Risk of suboptimal resource allocation.

Balanced Approach

A combination of these approaches often yields the best results, ensuring a balance between high-level strategic objectives and the actual needs of lower-level departments.

Forecasting Revenue

Since non-governmental higher education institutions depend mainly on student tuition fees and funding from their founders, precise revenue forecasting is essential. As part of the financial planning process, institutions estimate their income sources for the upcoming academic year. This projection considers several factors, including:

Enrollment Patterns: Anticipating the number of students likely to enroll in different academic programs. It is important to consider the rapidly changing demographic characteristics of students. In recent years in Uzbekistan, the number of traditional college-age students (18–19 years old) has been increasing at a faster rate compared to graduates aged 20–25 and older (Figure 2). Analyzing this trend allows non-state higher education institutions (NOTT) to refine their marketing strategies by identifying which student segments to prioritize (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Admission Trends from 2022 to 2024.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Effective financial planning is essential for the sustainability and competitiveness of non-state higher education institutions (NSHEIs) in Uzbekistan. This study highlights the importance of diversified funding, strategic budgeting, and accurate revenue forecasting. As financial responsibility shifts from government support to students and private sectors, NSHEIs must adopt self-sustaining models.

By integrating structured budgeting methods and adapting to changing enrollment trends, institutions can enhance financial resilience and long-term stability. A strategic approach to financial planning will enable NSHEIs to improve service quality and contribute to the sustainable development of Uzbekistan's higher education sector.

References:

1. Valiev, Sh. E., & Khurramov, J. R. (2022). Features of financial management organization in non-state universities of Uzbekistan. *Ekonomika i predprinimatelstvo*, (10).
2. Meliksetyan, S. N. (2016). Features of financial planning in higher education institutions. *Financial Analytics: Problems and Solutions*, 5, 12–27.
3. Mirkasimov, B. (n.d.). New Uzbekistan strengthens its position by relying on higher education, science, and innovation. *Uzbekistan.org.ua*. Retrieved from <https://uzbekistan.org.ua/ru/news/6885-noviy-uzbekistan-ukreplyaet-sv.html>.
4. Rasulov, A. (2024, August 7). Reforms in the higher education system of Uzbekistan aimed at preparing competitive personnel. *The Asia Today*. Retrieved from <https://uzbekistan.org.ua/ru/news/6885-noviy-uzbekistan-ukreplyaet-sv>.
5. Karlibaeva, G. (2023). Analysis of financial resource allocation in higher education institutions. *Iqtisodiy taraqqiyot va tahlil*, (October 2024).
6. Kuvondiqov, F. (2024). Optimizing costs and improving the financing system of non-governmental higher education institutions. *Aktuar Moliya va Buxgalteriya Hisobi Ilmiy Jurnal*, 4(1), 31–38.

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